

D6 – Report on integration of technical system: Kosovo

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1 Introduction

The aim of WP1 of the SEEDS project is to implement the various features of the data service establishment plans. This includes organisational, policy, and technical developments, all geared up toward preparing for “day one” of the new data services in partner countries.

The last activity of WP1 is the integration of the archiving system (chosen in D9 - Report on technical improvements) into the technical infrastructure of the partner institutions. Besides creating a set of policy documents for the data services (see D5 - Policy and procedures document) and new individual websites (see D11), it involves the development of a technical prototype that will allow for the basic archiving functions, following the OAIS model: ingest, preservation, and dissemination. Thus, as a key result of the SEEDS project, the data services have now chosen the tools and have the capacity to take in new social science data, and then to properly document, store, and distribute these data, all according to international standards.

This deliverable describes the technical prototype and its related processes. The purpose is to provide the tools and processes that will allow the new data services to begin building their data collections, to structure their data and metadata in ways to allow for discovery and reuse, to store and secure data for the long-term, and to provide the conditions and platforms for data access for their future users. In sum, the prototype supplies a basic archiving infrastructure, with all needed hardware and software.

As has been the case in all previous project outputs, the intention was to maintain as much commonalities as possible across the six new data services, and this is especially true for the established technical platform. Common and compatible tools will allow for future data and information sharing, as well as for synergies across the national services.

1.1 OAIS Model

The rapid growth of digital material in both volume and complexity, the rising expectations of archives’ users for access services, and the emerging digital preservation strategies, have all contributed to the definition of digital archive functions. The functionalities and procedures of a digital archive have been collected into the OAIS reference model, which became an ISO standard in 2003 (ISO 14721:2003). The OAIS provides both a functional model – the specific tasks performed by the archive, such as storage or access – and a corresponding information model, which includes a model for the creation of metadata to support long-term maintenance and access (see figure 1-1).

Figure 1-1: OAIS Functional Entities

The OAIS reference model is separated into six functional entities: Ingest, Data Management, Archival Storage, Preservation Planning, Administration, and Access. Outside the OAIS are the Producer (data producers, depositors, researchers), the Consumer (readers, researchers, academics, public, user community), and the Management (data managers, archivists, programmers, database managers, data centre managers). The data within the OAIS are represented as information packages (IPs). Each information package consists of metadata and physical files. There are three types of IPs: submission information package (SIP), archival information package (AIP), and dissemination information package (DIP).

2 Functional Specifications

2.1 Conceptual Model and Workflow

2.1.1 Ingest

Ingest provides the services and functions to accept SIPs from the Producer and prepare the content for Archival Storage and Data Management within the archive (see figure 2-2).

Figure 2-2: Functions of Ingest

Receive submission: The submission of the research data can be done by email, in person (USB, CD or similar media) or by giving the users access to upload the research. Each submission received will be documented by two persons planned to be in charge to manage the archive.

Quality Assurance: The depositor will have to sign a contract, that will ensure that the submission meets the deposit requirements. The requirements will be determined later. The depositor shall use only accepted file formats for submission (determined in 2.3.), for other types of file formats the conversion to the appropriate formats shall be done by team management support. The administration team will be responsible for quality management. Each submission received shall go through the quality control.

AIP shall be generated as a result of SIP processing, which will then be the base for DIP. During this process of generating AIP, two activities will be done; rearrangement of data and decisions about the description level. This process will include the file format conversions, reorganization, repackaging and other transformations of the content information in the SIP. All transformations shall be documented.

2.1.2 Archival Storage

Archival Storage provides the services and functions for the storage maintenance and retrieval of AIPs (see figure 2-3). Archival Storage functions include receiving AIPs from Ingest and adding them to permanent storage, managing the storage hierarchy, refreshing the media on which archive holdings are stored, migrating files into the archival formats, performing routine and special error checking and providing disaster recovery capabilities.

Figure 2-3: Functions of the Archival Storage

Our team is trying to establish a secure environment, which will ensure the CIA (confidentiality, integrity and long-time accessibility) of the digital materials. And this can be done by implementing a strategy that will define the digital material security, the possibilities of mirroring the information in order to have an offsite backup and ensuring that the digital materials are eligible for new technologies and updates. Disaster recovery plan shall be planned within the CIA strategy.

2.1.3 Data Management

Data Management provides the services and functions for populating, maintaining and accessing both metadata, which identify and document repository holdings, and administrative data, used to manage the repository (see figure 2-4).

Figure 2-4: Functions of Data Management

Data Management shall be conducted by the quality management control, and involves 4 phases of control (plan, do, check, and act). Through this control we will ensure the maintenance of all archived information. As required by the quality management standard, the digital material shall follow the procedures of control, therefore all data submitted shall pass the administration control and will ensure long-term access.

2.1.4 Administration

Administration provides the services and functions for the overall operation of the archive system (see figure 2-5). Administration functions include soliciting and negotiating submission agreements

with the Producer, auditing submissions to ensure that they meet archive standards, and maintaining configuration management of system hardware and software. It is also responsible for establishing and maintaining archive standards and policies, providing user support, and activating stored requests.

Figure 2-5: Functions of Administration

Submission agreement will be done between our Head of data Archive and the Depositor. This submission agreement will ensure both parties that the depositor shall meet the necessary requirements. The necessary requirements mean that the quality of the data will be as agreed. As for the sensitivity of the data, the depositor shall decide for the accessibility of the data. In our Data Archive we will have 2 levels of data accessibility:

Open data; for all the researchers

Restricted data; that would require special permission in order to have access

2.1.5 Preservation Planning

Preservation Planning provides the services and functions for monitoring the environment of the archive and making recommendations to ensure that the information stored in the archive remain accessible over a long-term, even if the original computing environment becomes obsolete (see figure 2-6). Preservation planning functions include evaluating the contents of the archive and

periodically recommending archival information updates to migrate current archive holdings, developing recommendations for archive standards and policies, and monitoring changes in the technology environment and in the user's service requirements. Preservation Planning also develops detailed migration plans, software prototypes, and test plans to enable implementation of Administration migration goals.

Figure 2-6: Functions of Preservation Planning

The Preservation Planning process is based on the Information systems management standard that is an international standard for systems and data security. As mentioned earlier our institution is aiming to establish a system that will consist of maintaining of the CIA (confidentiality, integrity, long time accessibility) within our system.

- Data confidentiality; starting with the submission agreement, our institution and the depositor shall agree on the level of data confidentiality.
- Data integrity; ensures that the data will be authentic, the documentation and the data file shall be the insurance for data integrity.
- Data long time accessibility; ensures that the system shall be implemented in a way that will provide uninterrupted and continuous access

2.1.6 Access

Access provides the services and functions that support Consumers in determining the existence, description, location, and availability of information stored in the archive, and in allowing them to request and receive data (see figure 2-7). Access functions include communicating with Consumers to receive requests and applying controls to limit access to specially protected information. This includes coordinating the execution of requests until its successful completion, generating responses, and delivering the responses to Consumers.

Figure 2-7: Functions of Access

For our users the data will be available under 3 different limitations:

- Open data; these data will be accessible for all users without registration
- Limited data; that will require registration in order to have access
- Restricted data; that will require an agreement with the depositor in order to have access.

Data in the archive will be available with above mentioned limitations and controlled access. The set restrictions corresponds to sensitivity of data and will be determined in the contract between the archive and the depositor in accordance with both parties. User of a data will need to sign user agreement where he will state the purpose of the use and his status. In accordance to his profile and restrictions on a data, he will be given one of above mentioned access.

2.2 Metadata Specifications

At KS DAS we will be compliant with the **Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)** metadata specification, version 2.5 or higher¹. To be more precise, USDAS will create the following types of metadata generated from accompanying documentation:

Complete documentation is available on the DDI alliance web page².

The DDI is designed to be fully machine-readable and machine processable. It is defined in XML, which facilitates easy Internet access. DDI Controlled Vocabularies³ and CESSDA topic classification are planned to be used. The use of a predefined topic classification will make possible future inclusion in the CESSDA data catalogue⁴ easier, since these are the topics that enable browsing in the catalogue.

The fields for ingest in the archive ingest tool are made using the CESSDA-recommended fields⁵, relevant for study.

2.3. Files and File Formats

There are several reasons why a data archive should be concerned with file formats: they exist in big numbers, are relevant during the whole workflow of the OAIS reference model, and are largely proprietary. File formats are subject to rapid obsolescence if they are not evaluated according to crucial criteria, such as open standards, ubiquity, interoperability, and metadata support. Therefore, file formats that are well-documented, non-proprietary and usable on different hardware and software platforms are much less at risk of not being usable anymore in the future. In addition, their

¹ Data Documentation Initiative (DDI): <http://www.ddialliance.org/>

² <http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Codebook/2.1>

³ <http://www.ddialliance.org/controlled-vocabularies>

⁴ <http://www.cessda.net/catalogue/>

⁵

<https://cessda.net/content/download/709/6350/file/CESSDA%20mandatory%20and%20recommended%20metadata%20fields.pdf>

frequency of migration and their costs of preservation are lower.

File formats are an important issue during the entire workflow of the archive (see chapter 2.1). In the functional entity Preservation Planning, the composition and attributes of the information package are defined. This includes the selection of file formats for the SIP, the AIP and the DIP. The decisions of the archive on which file formats are acceptable as archival and distribution formats are linked to the significant properties of the files (what aspects of the digital material we want to preserve). That is why it is important that file formats are controlled and validated, according with the available specific tools, already in the Ingest phase.

There are a number of tools on the market for migrating a file format into a more reliable and sustainable file format:

- *Native Java Image library* for most image formats;
- *Imagemagick* for most image formats, esp. Raster;
- *FFMPEG* for various AV formats;
- *readpst* for email;
- *Ghostscript* for PDF;
- *Libre Office* for Office Open XML, and word processor files – also shifts various office formats to PDF and PDF/A;
- *Inkscape* for Vector images.

When selecting target formats, the following criteria should be considered:

- Ubiquity;
- Support;
- Disclosure;
- Documentation quality;
- Stability;
- Ease of identification and validation;
- Intellectual Property Rights;
- Metadata Support;
- Complexity;
- Interoperability;
- Viability;
- Re-usability.

The selected file formats represent a summary of different recommendations from CESSDA partners and internationally recognised institutions: ⁶

File formats considered as appropriate for SIPs:

⁶ The formats highlighted in bold are preferred over the others of the same category.

FORS: Qualitative Data Archiving at FORS – Policy and Procedures:

http://www2.unil.ch/daris/IMG/pdf/Donnees_qualitatives_archivees_chez_FORs_-_Politique_et_Procedures.pdf,

UK Data Archive: Formats table: <http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/create-manage/format/formats-table>, UK Data Archive: Assessment of UKDA and TNA Compliance with OAIS and METS Standards, p. 89

<http://www.dptp.org/wp-content/uploads/2010/08/UKDAp90.pdf>.

- Tabular data: **SPSS portable format (.por)**, SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta), Excel or other spreadsheet format files, which can be converted to tab- or comma-delimited text), R (.txt);
- Text: Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf), plain text data, ASCII (.txt), Rich Text Format (RTF) (.rtf), Microsoft Office and OpenOffice documents;
- Audio: **Waveform Audio Format (WAV) (.wav)** from Microsoft, Audio Interchange File Format (AIFF) (.aif) from Apple, FLAC (.flac);
- Raster (bitmap) images: **TIFF (.tif)** ideally version 6 uncompressed, JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), PNG (.png), GIF (.gif) and BMP (.bmp) only when created in this format, Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf);
- Vector images: DFX (.dfx), SVG (.svg);
- Video: **MPEG-2 (.mpg2)**, MPEG-4 (.mpg4), motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2).

Compressed files are accepted as long as they can be uncompressed by using open and freely available software.

File formats considered as appropriate for the AIP:

- Tabular data: Microsoft Excel File Format (XLS) (.xls), ASCII, Comma Separated Values (CSV) (.csv; .txt);
- Text: Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A) (.pdf), XML (.xml), Standard Generalised Markup Language (SGML) (.sgml);
- Audio: Waveform Audio File Format (.wav);
- Raster (bitmap) images: TIFF (.tif);
- Vector images: DFX (.dfx), SVG (.svg);
- Video: MPEG-2 (.mpg2).

File formats considered as appropriate for the DIP:

- Tabular data: SPSS portable format (.por), SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta), R (.txt);
- Text: Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF) (.pdf), Rich Text Format (RTF) (.rtf);
- Audio: MP3 (.mp3);
- Raster (bitmap) images: JPEG (.jpg)
- Vector images: DFX (.dfx), SVG (.svg);
- Video: MPEG-4 (.mpg4).

In addition, file format registries are a way of helping to identify file formats and looking up format specifications.

3 Technical Specifications

3.1 Tools

3.1.1 Dataverse

KS DAAS will use Dataverse to cover all of the segments of the OAIS model.

3.2.1 General Communication

According to the OAIS model there are several different possibilities for how the data archive can communicate with the actors, that is the data producers and consumers. More precisely, it is the functional entities Preservation Planning and Administration that are responsible for the communication task. They include for instance the development of preservation strategies and standards of monitoring the community and technology in order to meet the needs of the producers and consumers (see figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1: Communication

3.2.1.1 Website

The most common and wide-reaching channel to communicate with the community is by means of an institutional website. It is the showcase for interested consumers and producers of data to learn about how data can be obtained and submitted. It is the platform where the policy and procedures, reports and publications, guidelines for data preparation, description of data protection, and other training materials are made available.

The website of KS DASS can be visited on:

<https://ks.seedsproject.ffzg.hr/>

3.2.1.2 Mailing Lists

A mailing list of potential users will be established by the KS DASS in order to inform Producers and Consumers about the latest news and upcoming events, such as training and workshops.

3.2.1.3 Direct Contact

A third way of communication is direct contact of the Producers and the Consumers or potential users of the data service through sporadic interaction on an as-needed basis (e.g., for workshops, seminars, and conferences).

3.2.2 Specific Communication

All the specific communications with the users during user registration and Ingest will be recorded and maintained via Dataverse. However, direct communication as well as via email with depositors and users will be possible. As we have not established yet, this procedure will be clarified within the launching time.

3.3 Technical Infrastructure

Since KS DAAS has not yet established its entire necessary technical infrastructure, the following chapter presents only an example of how a server architecture could be specified. In the future, KS DAAS will determine in detail all the technical specification needed to fulfil its submission, archival administration and access policies.

3.3.1 Server Architecture (an example)

For the implementation of the SEEDS project 2 servers are needed:

- Virtual server 1 (currently in Croatia);
- Virtual server 2 (should be in each partner country);

The Virtual server 1 is used for the hosting of each national web portal. A single WordPress application with 6 website instances (one for each partner) is installed for the national web portals (see [D11](#)).

Here is the detailed Virtual server 1 configuration:

Configuration: 2 vCPU, 2GB RAM, 10GB HDD

OS: Debian GNU Linux 8.2 (Jessie)

HA: Ganneti cluster⁷

⁷ <http://www.ganeti.org/>

The Virtual server 2 should be used for the national catalogues and Ingest/Archival platforms.

Here is the detailed Virtual server 2 configuration example:

Configuration: 2 vCPU, 12.0 GB , 100.0 GB

OS: Debian GNU/Linux 8.2 (jessie)

HA: Not Enabled

Both Virtual server 1 and Virtual server 2 should have redundant IT infrastructure, monitoring, and backup. In addition to local (on-site) file and database backup, there should be a daily automatic offsite backup solution as well. The local servers should be used for backup purposes.

The usage of virtual machines is valuable for prototype implementation and testing, but for the production system, the newly established archives should have more granular distribution of services. Sensitivity of data in the various components of the OAIS, requires us to think about different security levels of data and preservation requirements. To achieve this goal, the future architecture will be installed separately on different virtual machines, based on different platform deployment stacks:

- Website
- Dataverse

Each of these components have different deployment requirements (database, web server, runtime language stack), so it makes sense to separate components on different VMs to enable easy maintenance (migration when changing components, deploying different components for new archives in the future, firmware upgrades).

Looking at the current state of development and support probability of chosen software of the established data archives, it seems that a future change in the components will be probable. This is one of the reasons why the easy maintainability of the system is important. The staff of the archive needs to be capable of testing other available software tools (in a state accessible to them), preferably under Free/Libre/Open Source licences, by using the process described in deliverable D9-Report on technical improvements.

Since each application is installed on a separate virtual machine (and each might have its own set of issues/bugs), security issues are addressed for each virtual machine individually. This means for example that in case of security problems on the web portal, there will be no effect on the security of the archival copy of the data or any other component of the archival infrastructure.

All virtual machines should have two copies stored on different physical machines locally. Machines should be located in different buildings to ensure continuous operation in case of environmental problems in one of the buildings (fire, flooding etc.).

During the process of developing an OAIS based data archive, two distinct types of data required for keeping in the archive were identified - SIP and AIP, which require long-term preservation together with an audit log. This also requires the ability to check whether data is correctly stored on the media that requires checksums on the level of the file system (scrubbing). For this requirement, ZFS⁸ storage and snapshots using LVM could be implemented to provide a long-term archival copy of current prototype on different locations (e.g. in faculty building), which should be updated daily (from computing centre location). This would enable disaster recovery in case of one location failure. It is also possible to have multiple remote copies, if needed.

The management of applications and data could be done using Ganeti⁹, an open source cloud solution that enables high availability for virtual machines and provides data storage requirements outlined above.

3.3.2 Network and Telecommunications

The network infrastructure and telecommunications are accessed using the host organisations' systems: Centre for Political Courage (CPC) within the institute for Social Studies and Humanities (ISSH), at the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Prishtina.

3.3.3 Hardware and Software for production systems

Based on best practices and international standards for social science data archives, the data services have determined the hardware and software they will use.

Workstation computers that will be used by future archive staff for Data Management should include the following software: office tools; conversion tools; software for statistical analysis (STATA, R, SPSS); tools for preparing metadata description of a study, etc.

If the archive wants to use a proprietary product, they will have to buy a licence or use the existing licences of their hosting institution, if available.

⁸ <http://bit.ly/dc14-zfs>

⁹ <http://bit.ly/dc14-ganeti>

4 Conclusions and Future Development

In conclusion, the prototype described in this paper provides the technical basis for all key archiving functions, following the OAIS model. The new data services will be able on “day one” to integrate and manage new datasets, safely store and protect data, as well as disseminate data and documentation to users. Their technical systems will function according to international norms and best practices, even if some of the archiving workflow will need to be handled manually.

It should be noted, however, that while the prototype will enable certain basic services, it will not be as comprehensive or as flexible as the one used by mature social science data archives. Future work should expand the technical development to accommodate for a greater volume and variety of data, to automate more everyday practices, and to enhance communication potential and exchange with data producers and users. This work will continue for many years, and will build on experience, further training, and funding. Like any others, these new data services will have to adapt technically to the ever-changing research and policy environments.